
SCIENTIFIC PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF FORMING YOUTH'S IMMUNITY TO POPULAR CULTURE IN THE GLOBALASHOV PROCESS

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Annotation: The article analyzes the importance of spirituality in protecting the minds of young people from the negative effects of mass culture and in forming healthy immunity in the process of globalization.

Key words: globalization, mass culture, immunity, ideological immunity, spirituality, human soul, culture, pedagogical education, value.

As science and cultural development increase, the need to educate a person and heal his soul is becoming more and more urgent. The need not to “lose oneself” in the ocean of events is becoming more and more felt. In such conditions, only a person and a people who strive to develop their own thoughts, ideas, and their harmony with national and universal values can save themselves. “Because in the current era,” says our Head of State, “in a complex environment where various political interests clash in the international arena, only a people and society that has its own thoughts, its own life position will become an invincible force and will be able to build its future with its own hands and intelligence.”¹

From the above quote it is clear that every person should be self-controlled, have their own firm opinion. Indeed, this is so: a person is governed by the heart and mind. For a person with a sick heart, the interests of society and national needs are of no interest. That is why in the East the purity of the human heart has always been considered sacred. Our thinkers were afraid not of physical death, but of a wound in the heart, of moral impoverishment.

Heart, heart, religion and theology are pure concepts. The word "heart" appears 133 times in the Holy Quran. According to scholars such as Tustari, Balkhi, Nuri, Termizi, and Ghazzali, the soul is a divine secret within a person, and because of this, a person is even higher than the angels. The heart can see the essence of things, it is a mirror that reflects human actions, good deeds fill it with light, and bad deeds, on the contrary, darken it.

So, the true essence of a person is reflected in his heart. Any person whose heart is filled with light, goodness, kindness, and beauty can be recognized as someone who strives for perfection and strives to become a better person.

At the same time, the upbringing of a beautiful person, a good personality, is not

¹Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 5, 2017 No. PF-5106 "On supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan".

determined only by his heart. Along with the heart, the role of the mind is also very important. The mind is considered one of the greatest blessings and it constantly encourages a person to understand, think, observe, and reflect.

The most important aspect of the matter is that only when it is in harmony with the soul, heart, mind, and intellect can it literally serve man and humanity, because as Aristotle noted, "intellect becomes virtue when combined with the beauty of the heart, otherwise intellect is not virtue."²

The role of achieving harmony between the heart and mind in a person in the upbringing of a harmonious generation is given particular importance in the East. The great thinker Abu Hamid al-Ghazali, in his work “The Chemistry of Happiness”, likens the human body to a city. The mind is the minister of the king of this city. “When the king, the minister of the heart, acts together with the advice of the mind, and the minister of lust and anger acts under the command and command of the minister of the mind, the country of the body will be in its order. And it will find the path to happiness and create the enlightenment of the Almighty. And if the minister of the heart enslaves the mind in the heat of lust and anger, the country of the body will be destroyed, and the king of the heart will also be enslaved, miserable and destroyed.”

In our opinion, there is no more explanation for the issue raised. Where the heart and mind are in harmony, there is development, goodness, virtue, and striving for beauty. The disagreement between the heart, mind, and mind is the source of all contradictions, injustices, and injustices. Undoubtedly, in this case, the place and importance of the heart, mind, and soul are great.

In this regard, an unprecedented amount of work has been done in our country during the years of independence. Spirituality and enlightenment have become a priority direction of state policy. What is important is not when this truth is officially proclaimed, but when it is recognized and acknowledged by our citizens.³

The purpose and social functions of culture have changed. If earlier culture was considered a means of realizing the imperial goals of the state and the dominant political ideology, now it has become a phenomenon that ensures human perfection, unites and organizes the nation, and serves a single national interest.

As a result, we have reached the days that our citizens dreamed of in the spiritual and educational sphere. We have had the opportunity to return our national, cultural, historical heritage to ourselves. The truth that the existence of a nation is a reflection of its culture has literally begun to be established. The restoration of our national culture has begun to help determine our place in the world arena. In the

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions in Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021".

³ Aleuov U. New pedagogical technology - the driving force behind the theory of education. - Nukus, "KDU", 2011. - 180 p.

series of these positive processes, it is necessary to highlight the decree of our Head of State “On measures to strengthen the material and technical base of children's music and art schools and further improve their activities for 2009-2014”. If we may say so, this document is a serious step towards further enlightening society, prioritizing human qualities, and establishing the principles of goodness, kindness, and justice in the human heart.

At the same time, in the current era, when the world is becoming increasingly globalized and integration processes are gaining momentum in all spheres, it is extremely urgent to bring about strong ideological changes in the minds of some citizens of our society, especially young people. We believe that it is also important not to forget that the influence of the West is increasing in some of our young people, leading to the existence of vices such as egoism, selfishness, and disregard for the interests of society.

In such difficult conditions, there is nothing more important than increasing the effectiveness of our spiritual and educational work among young people. For this, first of all, it is extremely necessary to form a healthy need in our young people that will allow them to enrich their spiritual image.

A healthy spiritual need is a means that fills the human soul with light, goodness, and virtue, and protects it from evil vices. In order to form a healthy need, we must have the ability to analyze the current situation. In order to determine such a situation, in our opinion, it is necessary to pay attention to the following.⁴

First, what qualities are of primary importance in the status of our youth as individuals today: material wealth, achievement, knowledge, or raising the general cultural level?

Secondly, are the spiritual blessings created - works of art, cinema and theater, and media publications - presented in a way that reflects the interests of our youth?

Thirdly, can the activities of the state and various levels of government, especially at the lower levels, to effectively organize the leisure time of our youth and form their spiritual image meet the current requirements?

Fourthly, based on the nature of market economy relations, is it possible to be satisfied with the patronage movement that can help raise the cultural level of citizens of our society?

In determining the spiritual image of society, in forming a healthy spiritual need of a citizen, the answers to the above questions are undoubtedly important. The formation of a citizen's spiritual need is extremely complex and requires a certain amount of time. For this, first of all, a person must have a tendency to self-development. This is largely due to the issue of role models and examples in the

⁴ Ziyamuhamedov B., Ziyamuhamedova S. New pedagogical technology. - Tashkent: Publishing house of medical literature named after "Abu Ali ibn Sino", 2002. - P. 120.

family, neighborhood, educational institution, institution, organization where one studies or works, and, in general, in society. This is the first issue.

The emergence of certain "works" that degrade and humiliate a person, along with works that express his beautiful qualities and holiness, undoubtedly vulgarizes the spiritual needs of the citizen. What can be expected from a person who regularly "watches" and "reads" about aggression, oppression, and violence? Healthy spirituality can only be formed on the basis of spiritual wealth that expresses the transformation of a bad person into a good person, and a good person into a person of beautiful character.

There is also a third aspect of the problem. It is known that in a citizen, ultimately, in a nation, there are cases of a tendency to assimilate the spiritual "wealth" of another person and nation, to elevate them to the level of a "cult". For this, first of all, the culture of that person or nation is slower than the cultural development of others. On the other hand, there is little effort for self-development in the person and society.⁵

However, the Uzbek people are considered a people that, with their national and cultural development, enjoy special respect and admiration in the world. This is a recognized axiom. It is possible to form the cultural and spiritual image of the nation on the basis of instilling these national and cultural wealth into the consciousness of our people, placing them in their hearts.

We often talk about the formation of a healthy spiritual need, we give our opinions on its necessity - this is true. But it is also known that in world practice there is no single universally recognized way to form a healthy spiritual need. Such a need, on the one hand, is formed as a result of the national-cultural historical heritage of the nation, the attitude of citizens of society to this heritage, and on the other hand, it depends on the attitude of the state to the national-cultural heritage, to its assimilation by citizens.

Here we would like to give an example: A. Chekhov's works have been screened 146 times, A. Pushkin's works 89, N. Gogol's works 68, F. Dostoevsky's works 46, A. Tolstoy's works 44 times, and feature films have been created based on their works. The writer whose works have been screened the most in the world is W. Shakespeare, with 300.

Of course, the whole world, including us, recognizes the above-mentioned names as classic writers. At the same time, is the level of knowledge we are imparting to the younger generation about our scientists and thinkers who created and laid the foundation for the rich cultural and scientific heritage of the Uzbek people, about the rich scientific and cultural heritage they created, and about the level of

⁵ Ziyamuhamedov B., Ziyamuhamedova S. New pedagogical technology. - Tashkent: Publishing house of medical literature named after "Abu Ali ibn Sino", 2002. - P. 120.

conveying them through artistic images, meeting today's requirements? In this regard, it would be appropriate to publish interesting books, fiction, and documentary works on various topics for our young people, taking into account their age, national characteristics, and interests, and to create films.

The great thinker Abu Ali ibn Sina noted that there were 35 areas of knowledge in the medieval Muslim East, in particular, in the present territory of Uzbekistan, and described each of them.

Well, why are we giving such examples? The fact is that a spiritual need does not arise by itself, in a dry place. Moreover, it is impossible to form such a need of a student, an ordinary citizen, by administrative means. You can force them to read books, watch a play. But the administrative method in this way can have a more negative effect than forming the spiritual need of the student.

In this sense, it is very important to determine whether our work, our spiritual and educational activities among members of society are achieving our goals and objectives, whether they serve to form a healthy spiritual need. In addition, a healthy spiritual need ensures that citizens have free thinking and achieve intellectual independence.

Indeed, a harmonious human upbringing, especially the formation of the qualities of goodness, kindness, love for the nation and the Motherland in the hearts of young people, does not happen by itself. One meaningful conversation or dialogue can be more beneficial than hundreds of aimless, ineffective events. We all know this. However, it seems that there is another reason for the ineffectiveness of our events.

The heart of the youth is a heart that is being formed. If the process of formation is not correctly determined, then in such a situation there is a high probability that a person will fall into the virtual world. In the virtual world, some unusual changes occur in the human heart that have not yet been fully understood, and then falling into various pitfalls is analyzed as freedom. It is also known that in the virtual world, a person does not feel moral responsibility. Even, as experts say, the virtual world, its creation in the bosom of modern information technologies, is more dangerous than the invention of the atomic bomb. We believe that there are two reasons why some of our young people are falling into the virtual world and are becoming isolated from the real world: firstly, they do not have their own independent spiritual identity. As a result, they are attracted to things that are "outside", and they gradually lose sight of their isolation from the real world. Secondly, this category of young people does not need self-development, and this also leads them to a state of flexibility and compliance.

In order to protect our youth from falling into the virtual world and to fill their hearts with the seeds of goodness and kindness, it is necessary, first of all, to remove

such people from the state of marginality. Marginality is the state in which a certain person or group remains “on the edge”, “in between” without belonging to a certain social group, class, or stratum in society. In other words, in a state of marginality, this or that person may remain “in the middle”. “Leaving” the influence of society, family, and neighborhood causes a person who has fallen into a state of marginality to become careless, uneducated, and alienated from social life. The main “characteristics” of a person who has fallen into such a state are indifference to the problems of society, sluggishness, a weakening of the sense of involvement in surrounding events, and instability. The soul of such people is damaged. The chances of such a person being influenced by others are always high. There is no great difficulty in conquering their hearts. This is extremely dangerous for society and the nation. That is why our spiritual and educational activities should be focused on eliminating the marginalization that exists among some of our young people.

In short, a perfect human education takes place due to the education of a single individual. Clarity is necessary in education. If we can purify the heart of the student, if we can sow the seeds of love, respect and admiration for the person, then we will undoubtedly create a healthy spiritual image of the society, because in the East there is always a rise from the material world to the pyx world. Purification of the soul was considered as a step towards perfection.

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